

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Deployment and Verification of Custom Autonomous Low-Budget IoT Devices for Image Feature Extraction in Wheat

F. MARTINEZ^{ID}, JAMES B. ROMAINE^{ID}, J. M. MANZANO^{ID}, CARMELINA IERARDI^{ID}, AND PABLO MILLÁN GATA^{ID}

Departamento de Ingeniería, Universidad Loyola Andalucía, 14004 Córdoba, Spain

Corresponding author: F. Martinez (fbmartinez@al.uloyola.es)

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ABSTRACT Given the need for effective crop monitoring while reducing human intervention and workload, it is necessary to implement devices that operate autonomously and are durable. These devices must be capable of operating over long distances, operate with low energy requirements, and resist climatic adversities and external factors such as dust and water to function effectively in rural areas. In this work, we introduce a low-cost autonomous IP67 IoT vision device designed and implemented in a real-world scenario. The device is used for automatic detection of wheat characteristics in order to optimise human resources when monitoring the growth and health of crops. Equipped with algorithms capable of capturing and processing images, the device has been designed to be computationally efficient, cost effective and power efficient. The device utilises the LoRaWAN communication protocol and requires 2.878 W and has 3.5 months of autonomy. Furthermore, it leverages specific low computational algorithms that can operate with low-resolution images making them more effective. To test the device in a real-world scenario, an algorithm that measures the height of wheat was introduced using classical vision techniques, with 97 % accuracy. Furthermore, the device incorporates an ad-hoc trained YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 object detection machine learning algorithm for the detection of spikes and stubble areas, which achieves a recall of 71.1 % and a precision of 79.5 % for the YOLOv8. In the case of the YOLOv10, it achieves a recall of 70 % and a precision of 77 %. The results are validated by expert agronomists annotations and data collected via a custom created web platform for remote visualisation and decision making tasks.

INDEX TERMS Computer vision, object detection, smart agriculture, YOLOv8, YOLOv10, spiking, stubble, wheat, height, IoT.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. MOTIVATION

Wheat is fundamental to global food security, providing a fifth of the world's calories and proteins. Cultivated on 217 million hectares annually, it faces the challenge of meeting increasing demand due to population growth and the preference for wheat-based processed foods [1]. Investing in research and development to boost its productivity sustain-

ably is crucial. Globally, wheat is the second most consumed grain after rice, with an average annual consumption per capita of 65.6 kg. It is especially popular in North Africa, West and Central Asia, and Europe, with Asia being the largest consumer, accounting for 53% of the total worldwide. Its importance in the diet and the need to optimise its production is clear in the face of current and future challenges [2]. According to Spain's Ministry of Agriculture, a significant amount of wheat and other grains, totalling 80,365.10 tons, is consumed each year, with consumption increasing annually by about 10%. Efficient production is crucial for optimising

the resources used in agricultural monitoring, especially as the country faces serious drought challenges, ranking it among the nations most affected by aridity. Climate research suggests that the incidence of extreme droughts could rise by almost 96%, a direct consequence of climate change. Its dynamic trade underscores its importance as a commodity, crucial not only for Spain's dietary needs but also for the agricultural sector. Achieving these improvements requires adopting better agricultural practices centred on yield and sustainability. It is therefore important to be able to improve the control of certain parameters that help determine and improve the development of wheat.

For agronomists, knowing wheat height and its spiked and stubble stages is crucial for several reasons. On the one hand, wheat height is an important indicator of its overall development and health; proper height is associated with lower lodging incidence (permanent displacement of plants from their vertical stance), crucial for harvest efficiency and grain yield. Wheat plants growing with desired height characteristics are less prone to diseases and can better compete against weeds [3], [4]. Therefore, measuring height helps anticipate and mitigate this risk and can indicate the best time for applying fertilisers, pesticides, and other agricultural management practices [5], [6].

The spiked stage, on the other hand, is an indicator of crop maturity, determining the optimal time for treatments such as fertilisation or irrigation, and ultimately, for harvesting. Proper spike detection is crucial for timing the harvest and ensuring the grain has enough time to fully develop and reach the desired quality [7], [8].

Finally, another factor to take into consideration is dry plant residue, which accumulates at the base of the plant, forming what is known as stubble. This accumulation can indicate several things. Firstly, it can simply signal the wheat maturation process. Additionally, if the accumulation of dry leaves is excessive or appears prematurely, it could be a sign of plant stress due to factors such as lack of water, insufficient nutrients, diseases, or pest damage [9], [10].

Accurate and timely monitoring of these properties is essential to optimise management practices and improve wheat yield. Although traditional visual assessments are typically used, they rely heavily on the experience and judgement of the expert, presenting limitations in terms of precision, objectivity, and time resolution. Modern technology allows for detailed and continuous recording, useful for analysing long-term trends and patterns, facilitating planning and improvement of agricultural practices, saving time and reducing the need for laborious manual inspections, and providing objective criteria for the evaluation of agronomic variables [11].

To alleviate the exhaustive monitoring performed by agronomists, several alternatives have been proposed, such as using cameras on tractors, although this still requires an operator. Consequently, more autonomous options have been proposed, such as robots that monitor crops with integrated cameras and follow predefined paths. However, these

robots still need human intervention after completing their missions.

Therefore, static devices have been proposed that can offer constant monitoring, employing a processor, a micro-controller, and a camera as basic components, capable of capturing and analysing images without constant intervention. However, ensuring their energy autonomy is another challenge, which can be mitigated by the use of either batteries or solar panels.

The use of these devices in isolated locations uncovers another important aspect, which is the communication protocol. These devices must have communication protocols to transmit data and use cloud computing, optimising computational resources and energy consumption.

These previous advancements have motivated the development of this device. Considering that the device will operate at long distances and must function as autonomously as possible, low energy consumption is of utmost importance, as well as its resistance to climatic adversities and exposure to external factors encountered in the field. Emphasising the autonomy and durability of the devices can transform agricultural monitoring, reducing the need for constant human intervention and ensuring reliable performance in challenging conditions. It is also crucial that they are resistant to dust and water to operate effectively in rural areas.

B. STATE OF THE ART

Agriculture, in addition to meeting food demand, contributes significantly to both the local and global economy, and, hence, improvements in efficiency and the integration of technologies during its processes are of interest when seeking to increase production. This integration ranges from harvesting and using machinery like harvesters and computer vision-based collection robots [12], to the inclusion of IoT resources for identifying crop status and development, and using image collection methods such as unmanned aerial vehicles [13], [14], [15].

The evolution of IoT resources in artificial intelligence, especially in the context of agriculture, has been significant, marking a shift in the management and optimisation of agricultural practices in both software and hardware [16], [17].

One important aspect of this technological integration is image processing. Techniques used include noise removal, enhancement, segmentation, feature extraction, classification, and detection. These techniques utilise algorithms like PSO (Particle Swarm Optimisation), SVM (Support Vector Machine), BPNN (Back Propagation Neural Network), random forest, and deep learning, selected based on the crop type and required phenological data [18], [19], [20].

In terms of crop height determination, the technique commonly used is stereo vision. In [21], crop height is determined under a controlled environment, so applying this method to real crops in a scenario involving external factors present in the field requires more complexity measures.

In [22] it was possible to detect the height of crops by means of stereo vision, through the use of a disparity map in different crops, where the object of interest is taken as that which is a shorter distance from the optical system, discarding any object that may be found behind the plant, whereas in [23] it is possible to identify the height of crops at a greater distance and in an outdoor scenario although without autonomy.

Initial efforts for wheat spike identification have been focused on laboratory environments with controlled conditions, facilitating the accurate capture of the morphological characteristics of the spikes. For example, [24] explores morphometric analysis of wheat spikes using 2D images in a laboratory setting, allowing for detailed quantitative measurement of shape, size, and other physical characteristics. Similarly, [25] applies deep learning techniques for spike identification, also under laboratory conditions, demonstrating the effectiveness of these methodologies in controlled environments.

As technology and image analysis methods have advanced, it has been possible to extend the application of these techniques to the field. The implementation of convolutional neural networks (CNN) in the analysis of images captured directly in the field is examined in [26], enabling effective spike detection despite the complexities of the natural environment. On the other hand, [27] highlights the use of Mask-RCNN for accurate spike identification in field conditions. Another applicable method belonging to the CNNs is Vision Transformers (ViTs).

These advancements underline the evolution of wheat spike identification techniques. However, in all these cases, high-resolution images have been used because they allow for obtaining details to identify these spikes, so a new challenge is to transfer these techniques to low-resolution images.

Regarding stubble management, there is limited information in the current state of the art. A study conducted in a controlled environment has been identified [28], which employs machine learning methods. However, there is a notable gap in research applying these methods in real-world settings, such as on farms.

Among the notable object detection techniques is the AdaViT method, which is part of the adaptive framework for vision transformers designed to improve efficiency in image recognition. Vision transformers have demonstrated remarkable performance in various tasks. Although it is an interesting method, its high computational cost remains a challenge, making it difficult to execute on low-cost processors [29]. However, following this method, CrossViT has been proposed, which addresses the weaknesses of the previous method without significantly sacrificing accuracy. Although no applications in agriculture were found in the literature, it is a technique that could be useful in the field of smart agriculture [30].

Other methods that are being widely implemented in agriculture include the YOLO family (You Only Look Once) [31]. Starting with YOLOv5, which was the first to be developed

in PyTorch, many other versions of YOLO have been created for object detection and, in some cases, can also be used for segmentation, such as YOLOv8. The most current method is YOLOv10, an object detector developed with the purpose of introducing significant improvements in computational cost and prediction efficiency. In [32], the YOLOv8 technique is used for insect detection in crops, while in [33], YOLOv5, YOLOv7, and YOLOv8 are applied for disease identification in tomatoes. Although these results are promising in terms of precision and computational cost reduction, YOLO continues to surpass itself with YOLOv10 [34], presenting results that are not only better in accuracy but also in computational cost efficiency, achieved by improving the prediction of bounding boxes that contain objects. YOLOv10 has higher accuracy, especially in detecting small objects and in complex scenarios, without compromising inference speed [35].

Initially, agricultural image capture was performed with conventional cameras, either operated manually or mounted on transport such as vehicles. This method presented frequency limitations and still required operators. The advancement of technology led to the integration of systems combining cameras with image processing platforms on devices like Raspberry Pi and Arduino, allowing for in-field data processing without a needing constant connection to a central network [36], [37].

Using high-resolution cameras, capable of adapting to outdoor conditions [38], offers greater convenience and advantage when making parameter predictions but at a high economic cost.

Addressing practices that involve the use of functional devices autonomously implies more relevant aspects that go beyond the development of the algorithm. In precision agriculture, autonomous robots have emerged as crucial tools for improving agricultural efficiency and sustainability. In [39], it is detailed how these robots are adopting advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and cloud computing. The proposed architecture integrates autonomous robots with cloud services to facilitate decision-making and data storage. The data captured by the robots and sensors are analysed using artificial intelligence algorithms, such as MobileNet for wheat detection and YOLOv4 for maize detection. These robots operate autonomously in the field, following predefined trajectories coordinated by an intelligent navigation manager.

In [40], the agricultural robot BoniRob is introduced, which is used for plant classification, localisation, and mapping in sugar beet fields. BoniRob employs a variety of cameras and sensors to capture visual and depth data, demonstrating the ability of robots to perform complex monitoring tasks in the field.

Robots are also used for pest and disease detection, as mentioned in [41], and in various agricultural applications that employ RGB, multispectral, hyperspectral, thermal cameras, LiDAR, IMU, and GNSS technologies [42]. Although these robots offer numerous applications, their complexity in terms

of software and hardware makes them expensive, especially when multiple sensors are used. Additionally, despite their autonomy, robots are not completely independent, which has led to considering alternatives such as static devices.

In [43], PhenoBot is described as a device designed for greenhouses that uses specific hardware to capture images and apply deep learning segmentation algorithms. Using a Raspberry Pi 3 as the central processing unit, the captured images are uploaded to a cloud server via HTTP or HTTPS requests and processed using the U-Net model. However, the article does not provide details about the PhenoBot power system, similar to other devices mentioned in [44].

AICropCAM, described in [45], is a static device that integrates edge image processing, IoT, and LoRaWAN communication for crop monitoring. It uses a Raspberry Pi 4B for image processing and an Arduino MKR1310 for LoRa communication and energy management, charging rechargeable batteries with solar energy. This device is trained to detect maize, soybean, and weeds using algorithms such as CropClassiNet, CanopySegNet, PlantCountNet, and YOLOv2 for weed detection. AICropCAM can also send maintenance requests automatically if rejected images are generated continuously, indicating a proactive monitoring system.

In [46], two stereo cameras are used along with a Raspberry Pi 3 and a Pycom Lopy 4, utilising LoRaWAN technology to transmit the results to a gateway, allowing long-range communication. Although these devices present autonomous power methods, they still lack protection systems against weather conditions, which is crucial for field operation.

An approach to automating agricultural monitoring could enable farmers to have easier access to a larger number of devices, facilitating large-scale crop planting automation. Additionally, the risk of theft or damage to devices in unsupervised open fields suggests that expensive equipment could pose a significant risk. Strategically placed static cameras, covering the entire viewing angle of a plot, could reduce the necessity for numerous devices

C. CONTRIBUTION

This article introduces a low-powered, resolution efficient and robust device, designed to capture, process, and send data results efficiently. This device is called the 'vision node'. The node is built to withstand adverse environmental conditions such as dust and rain. The main development of this work is based on the hardware proposal for the node, its assembly, image collection, analysis of images, with images captured at Los Remedios farm in Malaga, also at Pozo Blanco and Fuente Ovejuna, Córdoba, Spain, using low computational cost algorithms for obtaining relevant crop data, and the transmission and visualisation of this data to a custom built visualisation platform. The remainder of this article is structured as follows: Section II explains the hardware, communication protocol and data visualisation on the website. Section III explains the nodes operation, the

image acquisition process, the methodology related to the software used for height detection, and the algorithm used to identify proposed areas of spikes and stubble. Section IV presents the implementation of the device in a real world use case. The work concludes with a brief conclusion in Section V.

II. MATERIALS

This section presents the hardware, assembly, and communication protocol of the node, and the custom visualisation platform.

The device consists of a compact and low-power computational processor, responsible for running the necessary programs and algorithms for its operation. Reducing hardware resources leads to cost savings, contributing to easier access for agricultural workers.

It also includes a digital camera, essential for capturing images of the environment. Cost savings is a priority, hence the use of a single camera per node, resorting to a metric reference object in the crop identified by the vision algorithm for height determination.

Furthermore, the device is equipped with a specialised communication component, facilitating the transmission of processed data to a central station. This central station collects the data and transmits it to a remote server. This server plays a crucial role in the secure storage of the collected data.

Finally, the stored data is accessible through a web page. This page allows users to see and analyse the processed data, providing a convenient and user-friendly interface.

The employed algorithms used to validate the operation of the node have the advantage of low computational cost, enabling local processing of captured images adapted to low-resolution cameras. Working with low computational cost contributes to solving problems that may arise in cloud processing or storage due to inconsistent and unstable internet connection issues, especially in rural areas where broadband infrastructure is often insufficient.

For the identification of wheat spikes and stubble areas, the YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 object detection algorithms was trained with images obtained by the node. The device is designed to operate in various industrial scenarios, especially in agricultural environments where protection against dust and water is crucial. Dust and rain protection is essential for operation in fields, where the device is exposed to natural elements. This allows it to function continuously in different climatic conditions, which is vital for long-term data collection without interruptions. Its versatility makes it useful not only in agricultural sectors but also in quality control for manufacturing, in monitoring beaches to detect litter accumulation and assess the health of beach ecosystems, and in monitoring forest health, where it can watch over tree health, detect forest diseases, and evaluate the impact of pests. Additionally, with modifications to the algorithm, it could be used to monitor traffic without being affected by the climatic changes it might experience, among other applications that require cameras and IP67 protection.

A. HARDWARE

The vision node introduced in this work can be seen in Fig. 1. The node has IP 67 protection in order to remain on the farm and outdoors in adverse weather conditions. The most important components include a Raspberry Pi 3, a USB camera with an OV2710 chip (model HBV-1716WA) that captures images at a 1980 × 1920 pixels resolution and Pycom microcontroller (LoPy 4).

The Raspberry Pi 3, which runs the algorithms, was chosen over other computers, like NVIDIA Jetson, due to its advantageous use in applications that do not demand high computational power and prioritise energy efficiency and cost reduction. Overall, the Raspberry Pi 3 has lower power consumption, which is ideal for battery-powered applications or scenarios where consumption is a concern [47]. Its lower price also makes it a more accessible option, and the extensive support community and available resources make development and troubleshooting easy [48].

The USB camera with an OV2710 chip (model HBV-1716WA) was chosen because it is compatible with the Raspberry Pi 3 and has a low cost compared to other cameras. This is an important feature because a camera with high resolution significantly elevates the node’s cost and its ability to cover the desired work area with the right viewing angle.

A Pycom microcontroller (LoPy 4) is used for energy management and transmitting processed data via LoRa to a gateway. LoRa is a wireless communication technology highly attractive in the IoT field, especially in applications where long-range coverage and low energy consumption are crucial. The LoPy controls the node’s powering on and off through an algorithm calculating the necessary timings and synchronisation of the captures and devices. It was chosen for its low cost and because it has the option to work in ‘deep sleep’ when it is not operational, increasing the autonomy of the node due to its low power consumption [49].

FIGURE 1. Node interior.

Fig. 2 shows the vision node hardware block diagram. An optocoupler is placed between the Raspberry Pi and its battery. The Pycom microcontroller can activate or deactivate the optocoupler with one of its digital outputs, interrupting the Raspberry Pi power supply when it is not running code, thus prolonging the node’s autonomy.

Under normal field operating conditions, the node is powered by its internal batteries, powering both the LoPy and the Raspberry Pi, although the Raspberry Pi requires the inclusion of a boost converter to meet working operating parameters. However, it has on/off switches SW_1 and SW_2 that allow powering down both the Raspberry Pi and the microcontroller respectively, by cutting off the power supply from the batteries, and enabling external power through an external waterproof USB connection for local operations. These batteries are measured through an additional Analogue to digital converter (ADC), since the resolution of the LoPy’s analogue inputs is not sufficient.

The node manages image acquisition, and the images are processed locally on the Raspberry Pi, as LoRa is not capable of supporting the transmission of such large amounts of data. Consequently, only the data derived from algorithmic processing is transmitted. This approach is advantageous in remote areas where there is neither internet access nor a power supply.

FIGURE 2. Hardware diagram.

The node is installed in a vertical position on a pole, with a joint allowing the nodes viewing angle to be changed, covering as much of the plot as possible.

For assembling these nodes, a hole 0.5 m deep must be dug into the ground. A base is then inserted to fix a support post about 2 m in height and at a distance of 2 m from the crop. At this distance, the visual area covered by the vision node encompasses an area of 10.8 m², covering 2.4 meters vertically and 4.5 m horizontally. The base is covered with soil, and anchor lines with pegs are added to ensure the node’s stability even on very windy days. Finally, the node is screwed onto the post. The result of the node assembly is shown in Fig. 3.

FIGURE 3. Vision node deployed on the farm.

B. COMMUNICATION PROTOCOL AND DATA VISUALISATION

Fig. 4 shows the communication protocol scheme designed for the node. As shown in the diagram, it is a star-shaped data transmission architecture. This architecture features a central gateway that requires an internet connection, which can be provided via WiFi or a 3G SIM. The distance between the gateway and the vision node is 500 m. The gateway is typically situated at a high-elevation station, equipped with a long-range antenna to maximise its range. This antenna also lessens the likelihood of packet loss, thus creating a more robust system. The data transmitted from the node is sent to a specific IoT platform named ‘The Things Stack’ (TTS). The LoRaWAN technology selected is ideal for long-distance and low-energy data transmission.

Information from TTS is periodically acquired by an MQTT server, which acts as a subscriber, downloading the data to insert into a custom MongoDB database.

FIGURE 4. Communication protocol.

C. AGRITOOL

To access the data, a ‘‘Machine to Machine’’ MQTT protocol is used which subscribes to TTS, where the data from the node is located. This data is then inserted into a NoSQL MongoDB

database through custom coding, entirely developed from scratch in Python. Additionally, the Agritool website has been built from the ground up using the Yii2 framework, which employs PHP as its programming language.

The Agritool platform created consists of four main functions: i) ‘‘dashboard’’, which includes real-time monitoring of fundamental metrics and data; ii) ‘‘visualisation’’, which provides options to create and display customised graphs, iii) ‘‘download’’, allowing data download in multiple formats for further analysis; and iv) ‘‘Manage’’, enabling the management of users and their privileges.

For practical purposes, it offers the ability to choose the desired data from all or specific devices, facilitating management when dealing with multiple devices and available parameters. Once the parameters and the devices of interest are selected, a graph of the parameter’s behaviour is displayed. It is possible to view different graphs corresponding to various parameters on the same dashboard simultaneously, considering that the horizontal axis refers to the dates and the vertical axis corresponds to the magnitude. Bearing in mind that each graph is independent of the other and despite being drawn on the same coordinate axis, each one has its own associated magnitude. If the scale of one magnitude fluctuates within a range of values that are disparate compared to other parameters, you can use the tool that allows zooming in on specific areas of the graph, which is reversible if one wishes to return to the original state. The website also offers the option to visualise tables or download the data in different formats such as.xls or.csv.

In the management section, users have the ability to assign new users and designate their specific roles. These roles include administrator, researcher, and producer. The producer role is limited to accessing only the visualisation and dashboard features. Whereas administrators and researchers have access to the same features, the key distinction lies in the researcher’s inability to manage the administrator’s account. The Agritools web application also has the versatility that through URLs, data queries can be made.

III. METHODS

This section details the operation of the node, integrating the previously mentioned materials, the conditions for image capture, and the proposed algorithms for automatic detection of crop height, spikes, and stubble areas.

A. NODE OPERATION

Working on farms means that nodes are isolated from certain basic resources such as an internet connection, and even electrical power. Therefore, communication must occur through devices that allow long-distance communication while consuming minimal battery power. Due to these constraints, transmitting images is not a viable option, and instead, images are stored on a local SD card. Consequently, the following step in the process involves the Raspberry Pi automatically checking for existing folders or creating new ones for photo storage, ensuring camera connections,

FIGURE 5. Node operation.

and proceeding with image capture. Once an image has been captured, the algorithms can be executed to process it accordingly.

A message with data from the algorithm is then created and transmitted, establishing communication between the Raspberry Pi and LoPy4 to confirm the successful transmission of data to the cloud.

The messages sent contain data related to the parameters of interest for wheat. The areas of heading and the areas with stubble are indicated in a binary manner, where 0 indicates absence and 1 indicates presence, and the height is indicated in centimetres. Additionally, the battery percentage of both the LoPy 4 and the Raspberry Pi is sent to allow for the planning of maintenance such as battery changes.

The operation of the node is shown in Fig. 5 as follows: The LoPy wakes up and provides power to the Raspberry Pi, waiting for a message from it. Meanwhile, the Raspberry Pi starts running algorithms in the background, including an image capture algorithm and algorithms for calculating specific parameters for future computations. Upon completion of the execution, the Raspberry Pi generates a message as a result and transmits it back to the LoPy. If the LoPy receives the message, it sends a shutdown command to the Raspberry Pi; otherwise, it waits another 2 minutes for the message. Once this communication between the LoPy and the Raspberry Pi is completed, the LoPy turns off the Raspberry Pi.

Additionally, the LoPy tries to connect to the LoRa network for 5 minutes; if it is successful, it sends a message

FIGURE 6. Timeline for the update of the image capture schedule considering a frequency of twice a day.

FIGURE 7. Height calculation diagram.

through this connection. The message is captured by the gateway and transmitted over the internet to TTS. Finally, the LoPy enters a low-power mode until the next cycle.

The ideal schedule for image capture varies with the current seasons, which is why the option to remotely adjust the capture schedule was proposed to make adjustments according to the current season. Additionally, the option to change the number of captures for future applications was incorporated, taking into account two starting periods per day. This is done by accessing TTS, which is responsible for sending a message to the node. This message must specify four parameters that denote the specific order to change the node’s power-on time: t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4 .

Fig. 6 shows a timeline that allows a better identification of these parameters, the first parameter being t_1 , which is the time between the initially scheduled time on the node and the new time one wants to set. That is, t_1 is only used once, when the node is deployed and turned on for the first time. It is useful so the farmer can configure it and install the node with sufficient time to deploy the node. The second parameter, t_2 , which is the time between each capture, becomes particularly valuable when the objective is to execute algorithms repetitively in sequence. This approach is utilised when multiple captures of the same scenario are necessary to ensure the acquisition of a reliable image. Such repetitions are essential due to potential challenges in capturing data caused by external factors to which the device in the field may be exposed. For instance, unexpected events like a bird passing in front of the node at the exact moment of capture could disrupt the process. The number

of repetitions is configurable by code, but not by TTS. The third, t_3 and fourth, t_4 parameters correspond to the times of interest, bearing in mind that for this particular study, photos are required at two times of day, one at dawn and the other in the evening, thus corresponding to the third parameter for the timing of the first capture of the day at dawn and the fourth parameter for the second time of day in the evening.

In the particular case of this work t_2 is not used because only 2 captures are made per day, in the morning and in the evening.

B. HEIGHT IDENTIFICATION

To determine crop height, classic vision methods, which are efficient in terms of computational cost, are applied. A reference stake was installed alongside the crops with a total length of 134 cm, which has seven divisions in 10 cm segments, each division being made by a 1.2 cm thick orange tape.

The processes depicted in Fig. 7 are used to determine the current height of the crop, each block determining a processing step through which the image passes, which is described sequentially below.

The first step after obtaining the image captured by the node involves applying a mask to isolate the reference from the rest of the image.

The second step consists of applying a morphological erosion and dilation, these are techniques used in image processing to modify the geometry of objects within binary images. Erosion aims to remove small, irrelevant details by shrinking objects, making it useful for eliminating noise,

as shown Fig. 8, in which the grey pixels are those that are eliminated after performing the operation. Dilation, on the other hand, expands objects to highlight features, which can be helpful in closing gaps within objects, as shown in Fig. 9 Where the grey pixels are those that are added after performing the operation. These operations apply a convolution using a kernel, whose size depends on the application. Passing this kernel over the image creates a new binary image, focusing on preserving the structure of interest while disregarding the absolute pixel values. The outcome is a cleaner image that emphasises the desired shapes [50].

FIGURE 8. The image depicts kernel K_2 , the original image X , which contains a white pixel, and the result of the operation $X \ominus K_2$. In the result, the pixel that has changed from the initial value of 1 to a value of 0 is represented in grey.

FIGURE 9. The image depicts kernel K_1 , the original image X , which has two white pixels, and the result of the operation $X \oplus K_1$. In the result, the pixels that have changed from the initial value of 0 to a value of 1 are represented in grey.

The morphological operations of erosion and dilation over a binarised image X with kernel K are denoted $X \ominus K$ and $X \oplus K$, respectively [51].

The subsequent step is to apply a greyscale transformation. This is necessary for identifying objects using an OpenCV function named *findContours*, which helps to distinguish the objects. The following step is the vertical identification of objects, which isolates the reference object by identifying the largest vertical element, together with its coordinates. The next step is to eliminate the background, which consists of completely isolating the vertical object. Knowing its coordinates allows the image previously obtained from

the mask to isolate only what is contained within these coordinates, thus eliminating the other objects that belong to the background.

The upcoming step involves identifying the divisions of the completely isolated object, which is achieved by counting the divisions marked on the metric reference. It is also crucial to consider that the block representing the last division at the base of the metric reference can be a complete or a fractional division, as the wheat might partially cover it. Therefore, the proportionality between this division and the upper divisions must be considered to proceed to the final stage, which corresponds to determining its pixel-to-centimetre equivalence. In this stage, the divisions located in the upper part are equivalent to the standardised value of each division, and the last one can vary depending on the identified pixels. Once this is achieved, the length of each division is added, from which the total length of the metric reference should be subtracted to obtain the height of the crop.

To evaluate the performance of the algorithm, the error rate per photo is calculated as follows:

$$\varepsilon\% = \frac{h_a - h_m}{h_m} 100\%$$

where h_a is the estimated height from the algorithm and h_m is manual calculation with the divisions that we have incorporated in the metric object. The absolute error is calculated as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{\%n} = \sum_1^n \frac{\varepsilon\%}{n}$$

where $\varepsilon_{\%n}$ is the mean error absolute and n is the number of images captured during these months.

C. IDENTIFICATION OF SPIKE AND STUBBLE AREA

In this section, a convolutional neural network is trained and deployed to identify spikes and stubble areas. To do so, a dataset of images of the field is collected, labelled, and YOLO is trained over them.

The collected images were manually labelled using the Roboflow¹ platform, which allows the annotation of areas in the images, in this case, areas with spikes and areas with stubble. However, due to the low resolution of the images captured with the camera, objects cannot be isolated independently and are therefore indicated by characteristic areas instead of individual objects. In this manner, the object detector identifies portions of similar areas and thus indicates spiky areas or areas with stubble as shown in Fig. 10, where the purple rectangles are the stubble area labels and the yellow rectangles are the spiked areas.

Roboflow was chosen for its particular benefits in adjusting the YOLO model, which include equipping it to recognise areas with wheat spikes and stubble across a wide range of visual conditions. This feature is crucial when dealing with low-quality images, where details can be difficult to extract.

¹<https://roboflow.com/>

FIGURE 10. Labels in Roboflow, yellow for spikes and purple for stubble.

Roboflow is able to label areas using rectangles which helps to comprehensively cover and analyse different zones within an image, significantly improving the accuracy in detecting specific areas such as wheat ears under any visual conditions.

The algorithm must be able to identify if the crop in general has areas with stubble or spikes. This indicates a substantial dataset that should provide the YOLO model with ample information for accurate object detection under a variety of visual conditions. The object detection results in the image associate labels corresponding to spike areas numbered as class 0, and the other, stubble area, is associated with a 1 value.

For the development of an automated object detection system, an approach based on the YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 convolutional neural network architecture was implemented. YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 are chosen for this project because, unlike other detectors that are optimised to identify objects with well-defined edges, YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 can be trained to detect areas characterised by textures or patterns. Although YOLOv8 is normally used for segmentation, it also has the option to be used as an object detector. Therefore, throughout this document, only its functions as an object detector will be discussed.

This contrasts with models like Faster R-CNN, which, while generally more precise, tend to be slower than YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 due to their higher computational demand. Similarly, SSD (Single Shot MultiBox Detector) and RetinaNet, known for their ability to identify smaller objects, often operate at reduced speeds compared to YOLOv8 and YOLOv10, mainly because of their computational complexity. This capability offers a significant advantage when the goal is to identify features with more abstract characteristics or those that are not well-defined physically. Object detectors excel not only in recognising the presence of multiple objects within a single photograph but also in pinpointing their precise locations through bounding boxes. This YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 capability is critical, as a simple classifier might misidentify an object based on visual features dispersed across the image. In contrast,

an object detector can accurately isolate and verify the presence of specific objects at distinct locations. Given these advantages, we opted for a two-class object detector for our study. This approach allows for the independent detection of either spiked or stubble areas in wheat fields, significantly enhancing the robustness and utility of our detection system in diverse and challenging agricultural settings. In complex agricultural environments where the characteristics of objects of interest, such as spiked and stubble areas, may vary significantly, the precision and adaptability of object detectors are paramount.

The key adjustable hyperparameters in YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 are the Learning Rate, which defines how fast the network weights are updated during training, the batch Size, which indicates the number of samples processed before updating the network weights, and the number of Epochs, which is the total number of complete passes through the training dataset, which can be tuned for performance optimisation across different datasets. The model leverages fine-tuning for precise adaptation to specific object detection tasks. These elements enhance the YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 versatility and effectiveness in various object detection applications. Fine-tuning in YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 involves customising the model for specific tasks by adjusting key hyperparameters. This process is crucial for optimising performance on different data sets and may include adapting other aspects of the model, such as network architecture and regularisation techniques. The adaptability and effectiveness of the model in various applications is enhanced by this meticulous tuning process [52], [53].

For object detection, the YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 model, applying the default configuration provided in the Ultralytics public repository^{2,3}. The decision to maintain the default settings was made to assess the ‘out-of-the-box’ model’s effectiveness for this specific task, demonstrating efficiency and proven robustness. For this training with YOLOv8 and YOLOv10, the database has been divided into three parts: approximately 87% images for training, 5% for testing, and 8% for validation. This is suitable for a wide range of computer vision tasks without the need for additional adjustments, using the default values for batch size, learning rate, and other parameters, with the exception of the number of epochs.

Once the CNN model is trained, it can be validated over new images. Given a new image provided to the model, its output contains a bounding box over detected classes (spikes or stubble areas). The predicted bounding box is obtained from the model and is a rectangular box that is used to define the location of an object within an image [54].

In previous model of YOLO, to validate the model, the intersection over union IoU is defined as follows. Given a validation image, whose real class is labelled with a bounding box. Both bounding boxes are compared, using two indices:

²<https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytic>

³<https://github.com/THU-MIG/yolov10>

A_o denotes the area overlap, which measures the intersection between both boxes. A_u Measures the area of intersection between both boxes. Then, the IoU is calculated as the coefficient between them, as shown in the Fig. 11.

$$IoU = \frac{A_o}{A_u} = \frac{\text{Intersection Area}}{\text{Union Area}}$$

FIGURE 11. IoU definition.

In YOLOv8 and YOLOv10, is used the parameters called $CIoU$ (Complete Intersection over Union), not only considers IoU , the intersection of areas between the labelled object box and the predicted box but also takes into account the alignment of their centres, as well as the aspect ratio of the boxes. This provides a more comprehensive measure of how well the predicted bounding box matches the ground truth [55], [56].

$CIoU$ is defined as follows.

$$CIoU = IoU - \frac{\rho^2(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}^g)}{c^2} - \alpha v \quad (1)$$

where:

$$\rho(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}^g) = \sqrt{(x - x^g)^2 + (y - y^g)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$c = \sqrt{(w + w^g)^2 + (h + h^g)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$v = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \left(\arctan\left(\frac{w^g}{h^g}\right) - \arctan\left(\frac{w}{h}\right) \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{v}{(1 - IoU) + v} \quad (5)$$

where:

\mathbf{b} and \mathbf{b}^g are the predicted and ground truth bounding boxes, respectively.

$\rho(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}^g)$ is the Euclidean distance between the centres of the predicted and ground truth bounding boxes.

c is the diagonal length of the smallest enclosing box that can contain both \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{b}^g .

v measures the aspect ratio consistency between the predicted and ground truth bounding boxes.

α is a weight factor that balances the influence of v .

A higher $CIoU$ value, which can reach a maximum of 1, indicates greater accuracy in predicting the location and size of the object, and is an essential parameter for measuring the quality of object detection model predictions. This maximum value of 1 signifies perfect alignment between the predicted and actual bounding boxes, where a closer approximation to this maximum reflects higher precision in detection [57]. In this case, having annotations of very different areas, a high $CIoU$ value is not crucial for YOLO's effectiveness. YOLO aims to detect and localise objects accurately regardless of precise bounding box delineation. Thus,

in such scenarios, $CIoU$ may not accurately reflect detection quality; instead, factors like the model's object identification accuracy are more relevant for assessing YOLO's effectiveness.

The confidence score in object detection models, such as YOLOv8 and YOLOv10, is calculated as the product of two key factors: the probability that a bounding box contains an object (P_{obj}) and the probability of the most likely class (P_{class}). The first factor, object probability (P_{obj}), is determined during the model training phase by assessing how likely it is that a bounding box encapsulates an object of interest. This probability is obtained by applying a Sigmoid function to the logits predicted by the model.

The second factor, class probability (P_{class}), evaluates how likely it is that the object within the bounding box belongs to a specific class. This probability is obtained by applying a Softmax function to the class logits and selecting the highest probability.

Additionally, the Complete Intersection over Union ($CIoU$) score often evaluates how accurately the bounding box aligns with the actual location and size of the object. While $CIoU$ is not directly used in calculating the confidence score, it plays a crucial role in training the model and improving the overall quality of predictions.

Therefore, the confidence score serves a dual purpose: it quantifies the model's certainty in the presence of an object within a given bounding box and the expected accuracy of that bounding box positioning. A higher confidence score indicates a stronger belief in both the presence of an object and the correctness of its delineated boundaries.

On the other hand, for analysis during the training of object detection models like YOLO, several performance curves are monitored to evaluate how well the model is learning. The two main curves are the object loss curve (obj_loss) and the classification loss curve (cls_loss). The object loss curve (obj_loss) shows how the model's ability to detect the presence of an object improves (or not) during training, while the classification loss curve (cls_loss) shows how the model's ability to correctly classify objects improves during training. These curves are essential for adjusting the model's training and ensuring it is learning effectively.

When classifying, one may encounter binary classification or multiclass classification, where multiclass classification differs from binary classification in that binary classification only distinguishes between two classes (positive or negative), while multiclass classification handles three or more distinct categories. In both cases, it is necessary to compute the precision and recall. This metric provides a balanced evaluation of precision and recall by considering the area under the precision-recall curve [54], [55] and is calculated as follows:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}; \quad Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN},$$

where TP are the true positives, FP the false positives, and FN the false negatives.

1) TRUE POSITIVES (TP)

are instances where the model correctly predicts the positive class. In the context of object detection, a TP occurs when the model correctly identifies and classifies an object within an image, including accurately positioning a bounding box around the object. The criteria for a prediction to be considered a TP can vary, often involving a threshold for classification confidence and, in detection tasks, a minimum Intersection over Union (IoU) with a ground truth bounding box.

2) FALSE POSITIVES (FP)

occur when the model incorrectly predicts a positive outcome. In classification, this means assigning an instance to a class it does not belong to. In object detection, an FP can result from either misclassifying an object or correctly identifying the class but inaccurately placing the bounding box (e.g., no significant overlap with any ground truth object or overlapping with an object of a different class).

3) FALSE NEGATIVES (FN)

represent instances where the model fails to predict a positive outcome when it should. This happens in classification when an instance of a positive class is incorrectly classified as belonging to a negative class or not identified as an instance of the relevant class at all. In object detection, an FN might occur when the model overlooks an object altogether or fails to meet the criteria for a TP, such as not detecting the object with sufficient confidence or the bounding box not meeting the IoU threshold with the ground truth.

In the evaluation of classification and object detection models, performance metrics such as precision, recall, and the Average Precision (AP) play pivotal roles. These metrics are calculated based on the concepts of True Positives (TP), False Positives (FP), and False Negatives (FN), each representing a specific type of outcome in the model's predictions.

To construct a generalised precision-recall curve that reflects the overall performance of the model across multiple classes, it is necessary to integrate the results from all categories. This integration involves calculating a general precision and recall curve by averaging the precision and recall values obtained for each category, thereby providing a comprehensive overview of the model's performance on a multiclass scale.

The Average Precision (AP) metric, derived from precision-recall evaluations, provides a nuanced perspective on the trade-off between precision and recall at different thresholds [58]. Acknowledging this trade-off, the AP metric consolidates the information represented by the precision-recall curve for each class, facilitating a comparison of precision among these curves. By calculating the area under the curve, which results from averaging the precision-recall curves of all classes, the model's General mAP is ascertained. This offers a unified measure that encapsulates the model's proficiency in accurately

identifying and classifying objects across all considered classes.

To consider a YOLO model as acceptable in terms of mean Average Precision (mAP), values above 70% are generally considered good, and above 90% are excellent, especially for critical applications such as object detection in autonomous vehicles or medicine. However, for this particular application, an excellent mAP is not required. The mAP indicates a balance between precision and recall; as increasing precision tends to lower recall and vice versa, finding this balance is crucial, making mAP an ideal parameter for model metrics [59].

Additionally, the F1-Score, calculated as:

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}, \quad (6)$$

The F1-Score curve is calculated for each category, from which a general curve is derived by aggregating all the individual curves. This composite curve facilitates understanding the balance between precision and recall across various confidence threshold levels. It proves instrumental in selecting the most suitable confidence threshold value for the model as a whole, particularly at the peak of the overall F1-Score. This approach optimises the balance between precision and recall, ensuring the model's performance is finely tuned across all categories it detects.

When predicting bounding boxes, YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 operate differently. In YOLOv8, there is a list of anchor box proposals in the image. These are predefined boxes with specific sizes and aspect ratios that the model uses as references during object detection, distributed across the image in a grid. During the detection process, the model predicts bounding boxes within the anchor boxes and determines how much they need to be adjusted to match an object in the image. Once bounding box proposals are generated around possible objects and adjusted from the anchor boxes, a special filter called Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) is applied to ensure there are no duplicates. NMS reviews the predictions for the same object and selects the bounding box with the highest precision or confidence score, to prevent duplicate predictions for the same object [60].

In the case of YOLOv10, it does not use predefined anchor boxes. This means it does not start with specific sizes and aspect ratios. Instead, it directly predicts the coordinates and size of the bounding boxes for objects in the image. For each cell in the grid over the image, the model predicts the coordinates of the centre, the width and height of the bounding boxes, along with a confidence score indicating the probability that the box contains an object.

Once the bounding boxes are predicted, it uses an improved version of NMS mentioned in YOLOv8, called Cluster-NMS (Advanced Non-Maximum Suppression). Similar to traditional NMS, the model generates multiple bounding box predictions, each with a confidence score and an object class. However, in cases where the bounding boxes are very close

to each other and have high confidence scores, they are grouped and identified as a set of similar predictions. Then, within that group, the boxes are combined to generate a final representative prediction [61].

IV. RESULTS

This section details the implementation of the previously proposed methodology in a real-world case study. It provides evidence of the node's autonomy and the performance of the algorithms developed in a Python environment using the OpenCV library.

The images have been collected by the nodes during the wheat growth period at a resolution of 1920×1080 pixels, over 6 months, twice daily. This data is stored on a SD card in the Raspberry. Concurrently, agronomists collected crop information, which is used to validate the data extracted by our algorithms.

A. BATTERY

To assess the battery discharge profile, a node was deployed at the BIOAlverde farm in Dos Hermanas, Spain. This node was configured to acquire 14 frames per day. The necessity for the experiment arose due to the lack of a systematic study on battery life during the deployment in the wheat field; because batteries were replaced before they were fully depleted, thus preventing a thorough analysis of battery life under operational conditions.

The purpose of this study was to analyse battery consumption, focusing on the factors that affect battery life, such as charge loss over time and wear that leads to a decrease in efficiency due to prolonged use. Therefore, it was decided to use rechargeable batteries that had already seen considerable use.

To ensure the autonomy of the devices in the field, where recharging the batteries presents logistical problems, knowing the consumption of the devices is crucial. To reduce it, it was proposed that the node should only operate twice a day instead of only once a day, contemplating the possibility that right at the moment of capture there could be an obstruction with the vision of the node by some external agent. Another alternative would be to use solar powered devices, but they are more expensive and are susceptible to dust accumulation.

The battery charge percentage of the node is shown in Fig. 12, lasting 13 days. Faster discharge by the Raspberry batteries is observed, therefore the Raspberry Pi's consumption is used as a reference for calculating the autonomy life of the system.

Under the aforementioned initial conditions, we proceeded to calculate the node's power consumption, using the data shown in Table 1, where the parameters associated with the Raspberry are:

V_{batt}^R is the battery voltage, C_{batt}^R is the battery capacity, I_{on}^R is the current consumed by the Raspberry when it is turned on, I_{off}^R is the current consumed by the Raspberry when it is

FIGURE 12. Battery consumption on an experiment with augmented use.

TABLE 1. Parameters of LoPy and Raspberry.

	Raspberry		LoPy
V_{batt}^R	3.7 V	V_{batt}^L	4.8 V
C_{batt}^R	5.2 Ah	C_{batt}^L	2.8 Ah
I_{on}^R	0.7 A	I_{on}^L	0.06 A
I_{off}^R	0 A	I_{Ds}^L	220×10^{-6} A
t_{on}^R	0.07 h	t_{on}^L	0.07 h
-	-	t_{Ds}^L	23.93 h

turned off, t_{on}^R the time which the Raspberry is turn on in a day.

V_{batt}^L is the voltage of the LoPy's battery, C_{batt}^L is the capacity of the LoPy's battery, I_{on}^L is the current consumed by the LoPy when it is awake, I_{Ds}^L is the current consumed by the LoPy when it is in deep sleep, t_{on}^L is the time which the LoPy is awake in a day, t_{Ds}^L is the time which the LoPy is deepsleep in a day.

For the calculation of the power, P^R , the, the following operation is performed:

$$P^R = V_{batt}^R \times I_{on}^R.$$

For the calculation of the consumed energy in a day, E_{con}^R , the following equation is used:

$$E_{con}^R = P^R \times t_{on}^R.$$

For the calculation of the Raspberry battery energy, E_{batt}^R , the following equation is used:

$$E_{batt}^R = V_{batt}^R \times C_{batt}^R.$$

For the calculation of battery life in days, we use:

$$n_{batt}^R = \frac{E_{batt}^R}{E_{con}^R}.$$

Although the consumption of the node is limited by the consumption of the Raspberry due to its higher battery drain rate, the consumption of the LoPy is shown below.

The following are the power calculations for the LoPy when it is turned on:

$$P_{on}^L = V_{batt}^L \times I_{on}^L.$$

The following are the power calculations for the LoPy when it is in deepsleep:

$$P_{Ds}^L = V_{batt}^L \times I_{Ds}^L.$$

The calculation of the energy consumed during the switch-on period was conducted over the course of one day as follows:

$$E_{con}^L = P_{on}^L \times t_{on}^L.$$

the calculation of the energy consumed during the deepsleep period in one day:

$$E_{Ds}^L = P_{Ds}^L \times t_{Ds}^L.$$

Applying the data the results are:

$$P^R = 0.187 \text{ W}, E_{con}^R = 0.259 \text{ Wh d}^{-1}, E_{batt}^R = 19.24 \text{ Wh}, n_{batt}^R = 105 \text{ d}, P_{on}^L = 0.288 \text{ W}, P_{Ds}^L = 1.056 \times 10^{-3} \text{ W}, E_{Ds}^L = 0.0252 \text{ Wh d}^{-1} \text{ y } E_{con}^L = 0.02 \text{ Wh d}^{-1}$$

Once the consumption-related parameters have been obtained, the total energy consumed in one day by the LoPy can be calculated by means of the following equation:

$$E_{Total}^L = E_{con}^L + E_{Ds}^L.$$

The LoPy's energy E_{batt}^L consumed calculation is presented below:

$$E_{batt}^L = V_{batt}^L \times C_{batt}^L.$$

The following is used for battery life in days:

$$n_{batt}^L = \frac{E_{batt}^L}{E_{Total}^L}.$$

Applying the data the results are: $E_{Total}^L = 0.045 \text{ Wh d}^{-1}$, $E_{batt}^L = 13.44 \text{ Wh y}$ $n_{batt}^L = 532.52 \text{ d}$.

The autonomy of the Raspberry Pi, is calculated as 105 days, which is equivalent to 3.5 months, and satisfies the operational requirements for most field applications. This enables the monitoring of crops with long life cycles, such as wheat, without the need for frequent recharging. It is important to note that the Raspberry Pi device discharges faster than the LoPy. Planning scheduled maintenance is crucial to ensure the continuous operation of the vision node, depending on the crop life cycle. This implies that the device requires maintenance every 3.5 months to change the batteries.

Applying the calculation for the previously mentioned experiment, using the Raspberry Pi technique data, changing the on-time to $t_{on}^R = 0$, 49 hours which is equivalent to the time of operation per day, which corresponds to the Raspberry Pi's on-time for our case study, yields a result of 16 days. After updating the calculations for the Raspberry Pi in this new scenario, we have:

$$P^R = 2.59 \text{ W}, E_{con}^R = 1.196 \text{ Wh d}^{-1}, E_{batt}^R = 19.24 \text{ Wh}, n_{batt}^R = 15 \text{ d}.$$

While this differs from reality by 2 days, it is worth highlighting that batteries can exhibit variations in performance

due to the previously mentioned factors, resulting in this case in a 13.3% error between the calculated days and the actual battery performance days.

In Table 2, a summary of the vision node parameters is presented.

TABLE 2. Characteristics of the vision node.

Protection grade	IP67
Microcontroller	LoPy4
LoPy4 consumption transmitting	60mA
LoPy4 consumption in Deepsleep	24uA
Processing	Raspberry Pi Model 3B+
RPI consumption	0.7 A
Communication protocol	LoRaWAN
Range in rural areas without altitude	15km
Range in urban areas	5-10km
Range in rural areas with altitude	0.5 km
Remote control	Yes
LoPy4 battery	4.8V 2800mAh (4xAAA)
RPI battery	3.7V 5200mAh (2x18650)

B. WHEAT HEIGHT

In Fig. 13a, one of the captures made by the node is shown as an example. In this image, the operations algorithm applied is shown to determine height. In Fig. 13b, the result of applying a mask to the image is observed, clearly highlighting the reference object. For this, the range of values applied to the mask were identified, with the Hue (H) ranging from 33 to 93, covering all shades of green, since the reference is green. Due to the fact that the color of the reference coincides with that of the crop in the image, additional operations are applied to correctly isolate it from the environment.

The morphological operations applied consist of two erosions followed by one dilation. Fig. 13c displays the outcome of applying these morphological operations. Initially, erosion is performed using a kernel K_1 of size 40×10 pixels. This reduces dimensions to detect scattered green pixels. For the dilation process, a kernel K_2 of 25×40 pixels is used. This kernel is larger in dimension compared to the previous one, aiming to unify the green tones and create large objects to eliminate them, ultimately isolating only the object of interest, which is the reference object. In the case of erosion, the i^{th} pixel of the resulting image takes the minimum value among those found in the region around the i^{th} pixel of the original image, where *the region around* is defined by the size of the kernel. Dilation is the opposite operation: the resulting pixel takes the value of the pixel with the highest luminosity value among those covered by the kernel.

In Fig. 13d, all the small objects identified in the image are detected, where the one of interest is shown zoomed in, which is the reference object. The next step is to identify the most vertical object among them and use its coordinates to apply a mask as shown in Fig. 13b. The result of this is observed in Fig. 13e. In this figure, the divisions are finally identified to determine the height through the equivalence of these pixels in cm. The estimated height is $h_a = 82.2 \text{ cm}$, while the height

FIGURE 13. Results of the height detection procedure. (a) image captured by the node, (b) mask of green tones, (c) erosion and dilation, (d) small objects identified, (e) metric detection, (f) divisions identified.

measured by agronomists, which was estimated by them and not precisely, is 88 cm. A manual calculation has been made because, with the divisions incorporated, the height can be visually calculated, which is $h_m = 79.2$ cm, resulting in an error of 6.59% between the algorithm calculation and the agronomist, and $\varepsilon\% = 3.78\%$ between the manual measurement and the height calculation performed by the algorithm.

C. IDENTIFICATION OF SPIKE AND STUBBLE AREA

For the application of the YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 methods, a dataset comprising 368 wheat images was utilized. This dataset was augmented using data augmentation techniques, including brightness adjustment and horizontal flipping, resulting in two distinct classes. As a consequence of this enhancement process, a total of 679 images were generated for use in the model training phase. To accommodate the increased complexity and diversity of the augmented dataset, the number of training epochs was set to 1200. The dataset is richly annotated with 14,155 instances for spike areas and 7,901 for stubble areas. With the dataset preparation complete, we now proceed to examine the learning curves that will provide insight into the YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 model performance throughout its training.

In Figs. 14a and 14b, the box_loss curves from YOLOv8 reflect the model accuracy in predicting the location and size of the bounding boxes. Similarly, the cls_loss depicted in Figs. 14c and 14d assesses the classification performance within those boxes. Likewise, in Figs. 15a and 15b, the box_loss curves from YOLOv10 reflect the model accuracy in predicting the location and size of the bounding boxes.

Similarly, the cls_loss depicted in Figs. 15b and 15d assesses the classification performance within those boxes.

The steady decline in both training and validation losses suggests not only precise bounding box predictions but also effective model generalisation, with no evident signs of overfitting. Furthermore, the precision and recall metrics showcased in Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 confirm the model's balanced capacity to correctly identify true positives and minimise false classifications for both YOLOv8 and YOLOv10, respectively.

These results demonstrate the robust ability of the model to handle different degrees of overlap in object detection. These results underscore the potential of YOLOv8 and YOLOv10 for real applications that require a high level of reliability in object detection.

The F1-confidence curve for YOLOv8 is presented in Fig. 18, while the F1-confidence curve for YOLOv10 is shown in Fig. 19. In both cases, the optimal value of the confidence variable to balance recall and precision is 0.3.

In Fig. 16, a precision vs. recall curve for YOLOv8 is shown, obtained using a confidence value of 0.3. This confidence value was chosen because it balances precision and recall, achieving approximately 75.7% mAP (mean Average Precision), 79.5% precision, and 71.1% recall for an IoU value of 0.5. Similarly, in Fig. 17, a precision vs. recall curve for YOLOv10 is shown, also obtained using a confidence value of 0.3. This value was selected for its balance between precision and recall, resulting in approximately 74% mAP, 77% precision, and 70% recall for an IoU value of 0.5. The final evaluation uses IoU because it is a widely accepted and standardised metric for assessing the

FIGURE 14. Training data by YOLOv8: (a) Training the location and size of the boxes, (b) Predicting the location and size of the boxes, (c) Training for classifying objects within the bounding boxes, (d) Prediction of classifying objects within the bounding boxes.

quality of predictions. Precision measures the proportion of true positive detections out of all positive detections made by the model, indicating the accuracy of these detections. Recall measures the proportion of true positive detections out of all actual positives, indicating the model’s ability to identify all relevant instances. Together, these metrics help understand the trade-off between identifying all objects (recall) and ensuring those identified are correct (precision).

Additionally, another important parameter is the mean Average Precision (mAP), which is derived from the area under the precision-recall curve. The mAP provides a single value that summarises the model’s performance across all classes, incorporating both precision and recall, and offering a comprehensive measure of the model’s proficiency

A summary of the resources used for the training can be seen in the table 3

In Fig. 20, the corresponding labelled images for comparison are displayed, while in Fig. 21 and Fig. 22, the objects predicted by the algorithm are presented using YOLOv8 and YOLOv10, respectively. It can be observed that in the

TABLE 3. Summary of train results.

Model	Time(S)	Ram(MB)	GPU(MB)
YOLOv8	6054	7189,89	2058,37
YOLOv10	8252,29	148,45	335,81

prediction, more spiked and stubble areas are detected than in the labelled images. However, as the low resolution of the image does not allow a single spike, or an isolated stubble stalk, to be labelled in isolation, areas are labelled so that the object detector can identify similar textures. In the group of labelled images, not all areas have been completely labelled with the same size or completely covering the spiked or stubble areas, so that the object detector at the moment of validation does identify them as having similar textures to the ones it has learned. Utilising YOLOv8 as well as YOLOv10 a correct distribution of the detected classes, with the coordinates of the bounding boxes drawn and their dimensions reflecting adequate coverage of the image space,

FIGURE 15. Training data by YOLOv10: (a) Training the location and size of the boxes, (b) Predicting the location and size of the boxes, (c) Training for classifying objects within the bounding boxes, (d) Prediction of classifying objects within the bounding boxes.

as observed in the corresponding labels. While these images cannot be sent through the LoRaWAN communication protocol, instructions have been included that send states related to the parameters to the web. In the case of spikes, when five or more spiked areas are detected, the message of spikes area presence is sent. This value is the threshold against the possibility of the presence of a false positive. As for stubble, it must occur invasively for its presence to be considered relevant, so the value for the change of presence is higher than that for spiking, being this of 7 areas with stubble detected. These thresholds were chosen based on the annotations made by agronomists regarding the same crop, in which the detection results agree with these annotations.

D. DISCUSSION

In this section, the variations between the expected behaviour and the results obtained in different scenarios by the node are discussed. Regarding the hardware, since image

captures are performed twice a day at specific times associated with sunrise and sunset, and since the cameras, being low-cost, do not allow automatic adjustments in their parameters, these time slots are the most suitable for capturing functional images for the algorithm to work correctly. It must be taken into account that with the change of season, these times shift, so attention must be paid to this update. Although the node has the option to modify these times remotely through the communication protocol, it is not capable of adjusting these values automatically, which is an aspect that should be included to improve the system.

Regarding the algorithm related to height measurement, although it shows results with small errors, it requires that the scenario always be optimal, which is often not possible in the field when there is adverse weather. In Fig. 23, some of the difficulties witnessed during this wheat growing season are observed. In Fig. 23a, it is noted that the node's antenna has

FIGURE 16. Precision vs recall curve from YOLOv8.

FIGURE 18. F1 vs confidence curve from YOLOv8.

FIGURE 17. Precision vs recall curve from YOLOv10.

FIGURE 19. F1 vs confidence curve from YOLOv10.

been moved by external factor to the point of obstructing the camera. In Fig. 23c, it can be seen that the metric reference has been displaced by a recent storm. These mentioned difficulties imply the need for physical assistance to the nodes.

Based on the information presented in Section I about devices designed for similar purposes, the authors constructed Table 4 highlighting the advantages of the proposed device. It demonstrates that the node created for this study covers a wider range of requirements than the others and allows its use in adverse environments where there is no internet connection, while still maintaining high

resolution in image capture. Additionally, the functionality of remotely operating the camera provides greater versatility for conducting experiments.

In Fig. 23b, it can be observed that due to the variation in the behaviour of the sun with respect to the season, the capture has been taken outside the expected position of the sun before the corresponding adjustment is made. The same can occur during time slots when the sun is absent. However, these last two issues can be modified remotely. The presence of inconveniences like those mentioned can be anticipated by conducting daily monitoring of the values received on the website. Since the values are outside the expected range, it indicates that some external factor is modifying the scenario expected by the vision node.

FIGURE 20. (a) Labeled images.

FIGURE 21. (b) Objects predicted by YOLOv8.

FIGURE 22. (c) Objects predicted by YOLOv10.

Initially, the planned distance between the gateway and the vision node was approximately 10 000 m, considering the technical specifications of the employed gateway, which offers a range of up to 15 000 m. However, due to existing obstructions, such as constructions between the vision node and the gateway, data transmission issues arose. These obstructions caused interference with the data to not always be transmitted correctly and, on occasion, not to reach

its destination. This issue was addressed by reducing the distance to 500 m and avoiding significant obstructions, thus ensuring proper data transmission.

The YOLOv10 version shows a higher confidence value compared to the YOLOv8 version. It is also highlighted in the literature that YOLOv10 is capable of using less memory, which is also evident in our results. These aspects occur because it is an improvement over

FIGURE 23. (a) Obstacle in the camera’s angle of view, (b) Capture made with overexposure due to the sun, (c) Scene altered by storm.

TABLE 4. Comparison of vision nodes.

Characteristics	Our node	Stereo-vision solution	Towards an efficient	IoT based Agriculture	AICROPCAM
Cameras and resolution	Yes, 1920x1080	Yes, 640x480	Yes, 1920x1080	No	Yes, 320x320
Communication	LoRa	LoRa	WiFi	LoRa (among others)	LoRa
Remote control	Yes	No	No	Not specified	Not specified
Offline (internet)	Yes	Yes	No	Not specified	Yes
Consumption	1.92 mW LoPy4 7.77 mW RPi 3 model B+	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	Nonsense and everything cannot determine the consumption of the devices
Range	5-15 km rural 2-5 km urban	5-15 km rural 2-5 km urban	Not specified	5-15 km rural 2-5 km urban	5-15 km rural 2-5 km urban
Protection grade	IP67	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified

YOLOv8, particularly in the prediction system, as mentioned in Section III-C.

V. CONCLUSION

The vision node is an efficient piece of hardware for agriculture, standing out for its low energy consumption and cost, which facilitates its autonomous use in the field and its accessibility to agronomists. Its algorithm, in addition to being economical in computational terms, is reliable and contributes to the standardisation of measurements in agronomic parameters, avoiding subjective judgments made by humans. It primarily serves to validate the hardware’s robust functionality, which could be seen as versatile for measuring other crops if the appropriate algorithms are implemented. The vision node requires maintenance within a period of 3.5 months under optimal operating conditions or at varying intervals depending on external factors such as climate. Its ability to transmit data allows remote identification of when intervention is necessary, thus improving management and efficiency in maintenance. The device has been operating in outdoor conditions for 6 months without any issues due to the mentioned exposure, thus proving its IP67 safety rating.

The training model demonstrated a notable ability to identify objects that had not been labelled during the annotation phase, suggesting effective generalisation beyond the provided training data. The error in the height calculation is about 3%, and for object detection, by YOLOv8 75.7 mAP, %recall of 71.1% and a precision of 79.5%, while by YOLOv10 74 mAP, recall of 70% and a precision of 77% were achieved. Although the YOLOv8 method has slightly

higher parameters, due to the improvements implemented in the new version YOLOv10, the confidence values within the predictions are higher for YOLOv10.

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F. MARTINEZ was born in Paraguay, in 1993. She received the degree in electrical engineering from the National University of Asuncion, in 2018, and the M.Sc. degree in electronic engineering, with a focus on renewable energy and energy efficiency from the University of the Southern Cone of the Americas, in 2020. This was achieved through the Pro-ciencia I program, which was financed by CONACYT. From 2019 to 2020, she taught with the National University of Asuncion, as a Teaching Assistant and has been a Professor with the University of the Southern Cone of the Americas, since 2020. In 2021, she began working as a Research Assistant with Universidad Loyola Andalucía (ULA). She has gaining research experience in energy quality, focusing on active power filters and model predictive control. Her current work is centered on computer vision and utilizing IoT-based devices for capturing images to monitor crop health through machine learning to detect key parameters. Her aim is to propel significant advancements in the intersection of technology and agriculture.

JAMES B. ROMAINE received the bachelor's degree in electronic engineering from the University of York, U.K., in 2013, the master's degree in microelectronic engineering from the University of Seville, Spain, in 2015, and the Ph.D. degree in physics from the University of Seville and the Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC) through the prestigious FPI Grant from the state. During the Ph.D. studies, he has specialized in the implementation of ultra-low powered and area efficient application specific integrated circuits for the use in implantable medical devices. This has a special emphasis on Epilepsy detection. He has published various works in respected journals, including IEEE TRANSACTIONS.

J. M. MANZANO received the Ph.D. degree in control systems engineering from the University of Seville. He is currently an Associate Professor with the Engineering Department, Universidad Loyola Andalucía, where he is also the Deputy Director of the Higher Technical School of Engineering. He is the Head of the Research Group "Optimization and Control of Distributed Systems." His research has focused on the development of artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques for system control, concentrating on stability analysis, and the efficient and safe operation of nonlinear systems using data-based techniques. He currently applies his research to smart agriculture and aquatic drones, among others.

CARMELINA IERARDI received the B.Eng. degree in biomedical engineering from the University of Pisa, Italy, in 2014, the M.S. degree in control system engineering from the University of Seville, in 2016, and the Ph.D. degree in data science from Universidad Loyola Andalucía, Seville, Spain, in 2021. Currently, she is an Assistant Professor with the Department of Engineering, Universidad Loyola Andalucía. Her research interests include cyber-physical systems, multi-agent systems, distributed estimation, and systematic reviews. She received the Best Academic Record Award during the master's study.

PABLO MILLÁN GATA received the M.Sc. degree in environmental engineering and the M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees in control engineering from the Universidad de Sevilla, USA, and the Dr.-Eng. degree. He was a Visiting Researcher with the Department of Electrical Engineering, KTH, Sweden, in 2011, and the University of Newcastle University, Australia, in 2012. In 2013, he joined Universidad Loyola Andalucía (ULA). Since 2014, he has been maintaining a regular research collaboration with Laboratoire d'Analyse et d'Architecture des Systemes (LAAS), CNRS, France. In 2015, he was a Visiting Researcher with the Department of Electrical Engineering, Marquette University, and Loyola Chicago University, USA. In 2022, he was a Visiting Professor with the Universitat di Bergamo, Italy. He is currently an Associate Professor and the Director of the School of Engineering, Universidad Loyola Andalucía. He has worked on 17 national and international research projects, being a PI in seven of them. He has authored or co-authored more than 60 technical articles published in ISI technical journals, books, and international conferences. His current research interests include distributed estimation and control for smart agriculture, autonomous surface vehicles, and cyber-physical systems. His contributions to the Ph.D. dissertation were recognized with the Best Thesis Awards of the University of Sevilla and the Best Thesis Awards of the Sevilla City Council.

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